

Enhancing Student Adaptability in Online Education through Federated Learning and Explainable AI

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Abstract

In the present digital era, the transition to online education requires the implementation of effective strategies and instruments to anticipate and facilitate student adaptability. This study suggests the creation of an Explainable AI (XAI) model that is based on federated learning. The objective of this model is to predict the adaptability of students to online education across multiple institutions, while also ensuring data privacy, security, and transparency. Federated learning facilitates the decentralized training of machine learning models, thereby enabling institutions to collaborate without the exchange of sensitive data. The interpretability of the model is improved by the incorporation of XAI techniques, such as SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations) and LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations), which offer educators transparent insights into the factors that influence student adaptability.

The research methodology entailed the iterative training and evaluation of the federated learning model, which was followed by the collection and preprocessing of diverse datasets from multiple educational institutions. The architecture of the model integrates deep learning and machine learning techniques to accurately and robustly predict both structured and unstructured data. In comparison to individual client models, the global model obtained a higher training accuracy (78.15%) and a lower training loss (0.64), as evidenced by the study's findings. These results emphasize the model's capacity to generalize across a variety of datasets while simultaneously preserving a moderate convergence rate.

The article introduces a novel method for predicting student adaptability in online education that integrates the advantages of XAI and federated learning. The resulting model is a valuable instrument for improving educational outcomes in a secure and transparent manner, as it not only protects the privacy of student data but also offers actionable insights.

Keywords: *Federated Learning, Explainable AI (XAI), Student Adaptability, Educational Data Privacy, Online Education Analytics*

Introduction

Online education has become an essential element of the educational landscape in the current digital era, providing learners worldwide with the flexibility and accessibility they require. The transition to online learning has been expedited by a variety of global factors, with the COVID-19 pandemic being the most significant. This crisis required a swift transition from traditional

classroom settings to virtual environments. This abrupt shift underscored the necessity of effective strategies and tools to evaluate and assist students as they navigate online education, highlighting the varying degrees of adaptability among students [1]. It has become essential for educators and institutions that are working to improve learning outcomes and guarantee that all students can flourish in a digital learning environment to

comprehend and anticipate student adaptability.

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a potent instrument in education, capable of analyzing vast quantities of data and generating insights that can radically enhance the learning experience. Explainable AI (XAI) has become increasingly popular among the various AI techniques due to its capacity to generate models that are both transparent and interpretable. This is particularly important in educational settings, where the trust and comprehension of AI-driven decisions are of the utmost importance. Nevertheless, the integration of AI in education also presents obstacles, particularly in the areas of data privacy and the ethical use of student data [2]. The security and privacy of sensitive student information are frequently a source of concern, as traditional AI

models frequently necessitate centralized data collection.

This research suggests the creation of a federated learning-based Explainable AI (XAI) model to anticipate the adaptability of students to online education across multiple institutions in order to overcome these obstacles. Federated learning is a novel methodology that facilitates the training of machine learning models across decentralized data sources, thereby enabling multiple institutions to collaborate on model improvement without the exchange of sensitive data. Federated learning is an optimal solution for educational environments that prioritize student privacy by maintaining data localization and exclusively sharing model updates, thereby substantially improving data privacy and security.

Figure 1: The traditional AI process

The conventional AI process is illustrated in Figure 1. The process commences with the "Training of Data" or "Dataset," which is then utilized by "Machine Learning Algorithms." The data is processed by these algorithms to generate "Learnt Functions," which are subsequently employed to make decisions or recommendations. The AI model's results are manipulated by the "End User," who receives the ultimate output of this process. The flow underscores the fact that the decision-making process in the current AI models is frequently a "black box" to the end user, thereby providing limited transparency into the process by which conclusions are reached.

The future of AI is depicted in the lower section of the diagram, which includes Explainable AI (XAI). It commences with a "Dataset" that is subjected to "Machine Learning Algorithms." Instead of proceeding directly to the learnt functions, the output is processed through a "Explainable AI Model (XAI)." This model guarantees that the AI's decision-making process is transparent and comprehensible. An "AI-based Interface" is utilized to present the results to the "End User." XAI's integration into the workflow guarantees that the end user can comprehend, rely on, and effectively interact with the AI's recommendations or decisions. An illustration of a figure operating

on a laptop while seated at a desk visually represents the end user. This figure is present in both sections of the diagram, emphasizing the user's central position in interacting with AI systems in both current and future contexts. The significance of user experience in the evolution of AI is emphasized by the consistent design of both

components of the diagram. The block diagram effectively conveys the transition from opaque AI models to more interpretable and user-friendly XAI systems, underscoring the increasing significance of transparency in AI decision-making processes

Figure 2: Federated Learning

Figure 2 depicts Federated Machine Learning (FML) data and model training in a distributed learning environment. This machine learning method trains models on decentralized devices or servers that retain local data samples without exchanging data. The technique protects data privacy and creates a worldwide model. The figure has many "Data" segments to represent the various data sources on different devices or places. The yellowish color of these data blocks indicates their importance as machine learning model input. Smartphones, laptops, and other IoT devices can generate and preserve datasets. FML Models locally: The light green "local FML model," connects each data source. Individual local models are trained without exchanging data with a central server. This phase protects data

privacy and security because sensitive data is still stored on the local device. Local training optimizes each model by learning from its data.

Global Model Aggregation: The diagram's centerpiece is the light crimson "Global Model Aggregation" block. After training, local FML models send their weights and biases to this central aggregation point. The central server or aggregator creates a global model from all local model parameters. This worldwide approach uses many data sources while protecting dataset privacy. Sharing the global model with the local models allows them to learn from all data sources and grow.

The federated learning-based XAI model will use data from several educational institutions to

predict student adaptation more accurately and broadly. This collaborative method improves model predictability and ensures its usefulness in many educational environments. By using XAI approaches, the model will offer transparent and interpretable predictions, helping educators understand student adaptability and make data-driven decisions for personalized learning interventions.

XAI models based on federated learning are a major improvement in educational technology. This research combines federated learning and XAI to produce a powerful and ethical model that helps educational institutions improve student flexibility in online education while protecting privacy and openness. This novel strategy could improve learning results by personalizing, securing, and addressing modern education issues.

This strategy is advantageous since it improves prediction accuracy while meeting strict data privacy rules. Traditional models are sometimes limited by the homogeneity of training data, which is usually from one institution or demography. Federated learning allows the model to learn from a larger and more diverse dataset, adding adaptation characteristics that may vary by geography, culture, and educational system. This improves the model's performance and makes it more adaptable to different educational settings.

Problem Statement

To develop a federated learning-based Explainable AI (XAI) model for predicting student adaptability to online education across multiple institutions, ensuring data privacy and security. This model will enhance prediction accuracy and generalizability through collaborative learning without sharing sensitive data

An overview of the article's contributions:

- Create an Enhanced Hybrid Explainable AI (XAI) model that forecasts students' adaptability to online education using ML, DL, and ensemble techniques for high accuracy and transparency.

- Implement a federated learning model for decentralized data processing across educational institutions, ensuring data privacy and security and enabling collaborative model refinement.
- Improve model interpretability by using XAI approaches like SHAP and LIME to make forecasts clear and understandable for educators and stakeholders.
- Improve local prediction accuracy by personalizing the global model to address data heterogeneity and adapting to the unique characteristics of each participating institution.

Literature Review

Muhammad Mubashar Hussain et al. (2024) [3] employed the Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm (LMA) in a deep learning framework to predict student academic performance using Educational Data Mining (EDM). The multi-layer neural network model used in their research processed large datasets to improve prediction accuracy. At 88.6% accuracy, the model is effective in early detection and intervention for at-risk students. Due to the intricacy and computational intensity of the neural network, their approach may be difficult for educational practitioners without technical skills to execute and interpret.

Djalilova Zarnigor Obidovna (2024) [4] examined the psychological and pedagogical effects of AI in education. A complete literature analysis and qualitative data gathering, including interviews and surveys, comprised the research approach. The study highlighted AI's ability to personalize learning and improve educational performance while expressing concerns about students' psychological well-being and ethical issues. This study balances the pros and cons of AI in education, making it strong. The substantial use of qualitative data may limit the findings' applicability across educational institutions and contexts.

Shahzad Akbar et al. (2024) [5] developed a novel model that predicted student performance under different educational situations using Deep Support Vector Machines (DSVM) and an Improved Conditional Generative Adversarial Network (ICGAN). High specificity and

sensitivity were achieved by integrating socio-environmental characteristics like parental education and family ties in the model.

Zeng et al. (2023)[6] propose a feature-contrastive graph federated learning framework for graph information analysis-based responsible AI. The framework protects data and ensures AI model accuracy and dependability in decentralized learning environments. Complex data structures used in social networks and recommendation systems are handled by advanced graph-based learning methods. This strategy enhances model accuracy and generalization over remote datasets without compromising data privacy. However, graph federated learning's complexity and processing burden may be downsides, especially in resource-constrained contexts.

Arrieta et al. (2020) [7] discuss Explainable AI (XAI) and how it makes AI systems more human-friendly. The authors explore XAI techniques including SHAP, LIME, and attention mechanisms to interpret and explain AI model decisions. The study emphasises the relevance of XAI in creating AI system trust, especially in high-stakes fields like healthcare and finance. XAI makes complicated AI models more approachable and trustworthy to non-experts by revealing their decision-making processes. Unfortunately, many XAI techniques are still under development and may not fully capture the intricacies of specific deep learning models, resulting in simplistic or partial explanations.

Renda et al. (2022) [8] use federated learning to construct explainable AI models for 6G systems, focussing on secure and automated vehicle networking. The authors offer a federated learning architecture that lets vehicles train AI models without sharing raw data, improving vehicular network security. This method protects data and boosts vehicular network AI system scalability and efficiency. The study shows how FL and XAI may deliver visible and understandable insights into AI-driven judgments in real-time vehicular contexts. However, maintaining and synchronizing data across several decentralized nodes is difficult,

especially for vehicular networks that require real-time performance.

Li et al. (2021) [9] propose a blockchain-assisted decentralized federated learning architecture to improve IoT federated learning system security and dependability. Blockchain technology makes data transfers and model upgrades tamper-proof and verifiable. The authors show that this strategy can strengthen federated learning systems, particularly in data breaches and model update integrity. Blockchain security makes this technology ideal for applications that require high data integrity and anonymity. Blockchain technology's intricacy and computing demands may limit its applicability, especially in resource-constrained IoT devices.

Kapoor et al. (2023)[110] use responsible AI concepts to develop resilient and equitable AI models for platforms and models. The authors offer a framework for transparent, fair, and accountable AI systems, especially public sector ones. Federated learning ensures data protection and XAI provides transparent explanations for AI-driven decisions. Its holistic approach to responsible AI addresses technical and ethical issues, making it advantageous. However, implementing such a structure needs significant resources and experience, which not all organizations have.

Xu et al. (2023) propose an asynchronous federated learning approach to increase smart public transport system efficiency and dependability. This paradigm permits real-time data processing and decision-making, even when data from diverse sources arrives at different times. Asynchronous federated learning systems are more scalable and adaptable to dynamic and complicated situations like public transit. Its great performance and dependability in real-time applications are its key benefits. However, the asynchronous approach may make it difficult to maintain consistency and synchronization across decentralized nodes, compromising system accuracy.

To enhance sustainability in higher education, Damanpreet Singh Walia et al. (2024) [11] integrated Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) Wallets into federated learning environments. The research reduced bureaucracy, reduced the need for multiple accounts across platforms, and streamlined administrative processes to improve digital education. The solution used SSI technology to provide consumers data control, maintaining privacy and security. This technique can boost university efficiency and support the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for excellent education. However, integrating SSI wallets into current systems is complicated and may need technical tweaks and a deep grasp of the technology by users and administrators.

Methodology of the Study

The study's technique is intended to create and verify a federated learning-based Explainable AI (XAI) model. This model's purpose is to forecast students' adaptability to online education in various institutions. This approach is meticulously organized to guarantee the safeguarding of student data privacy while improving the precision and comprehensibility of the predictions. The study is segmented into multiple phases, each focusing on a distinct component of the process of developing the model, ranging from gathering data to evaluating the model.

The initial stage is doing a thorough examination of the current body of literature to pinpoint the primary factors that impact students' capacity to adapt in online education. This phase also examines the many artificial intelligence techniques, specifically federated learning and explainable AI (XAI), that have been used in educational settings. The knowledge acquired from this review aids in developing a strong framework for the suggested model. The approach incorporates federated learning to manage distributed data across universities and XAI to guarantee that the model's predictions are visible and interpretable. During the subsequent stage, the activities of data collecting and preprocessing are carried out. Information is collected from many institutions to guarantee a varied and all-encompassing dataset, which is essential for the model's capacity to apply to a wide range of situations. The data includes a range of characteristics, such as demographic information, engagement measures, and psychological aspects, that are important for determining student adaptability. Subsequently, preprocessing techniques are employed to cleanse, standardize, and encode the data, so rendering it suitable for utilization in the federated learning model.

Figure 3: Proposed federated learning and XAI system

Figure 3 depicts the proposed Explainable AI (XAI) system based on federated learning. The

datasets consist of Demographic Data, which encompasses information regarding students' age,

gender, and socioeconomic status, all of which can have a substantial impact on a student's learning experience. Engagement Metrics are emphasised as markers of students' interaction with educational information. These indicators, such as participation rates, time dedicated to learning assignments, and frequency of logins, offer valuable information about a student's level of involvement with the educational content. Furthermore, Academic Performance data, encompassing grades, test scores, and other academic records, serves as a reflection of a student's educational progress. Finally, the graphic incorporates Psychological Attributes, which contain information pertaining to the mental and emotional states of pupils, such as their motivation, stress levels, and self-efficacy. Understanding the entire growth of a student and their ability to adapt to varied learning contexts relies heavily on these psychological elements.

The lower portion of the figure3 illustrates the processing components responsible for managing and leveraging these datasets. The Federated

Learning component is a distributed learning process in which data from many educational sources is utilized to train models locally at each institution. This method guarantees the security of sensitive student data by eliminating the necessity of sharing raw data across institutions. Instead, only updates to the model are communicated, which contributes to a process of collaborative learning. The local models are consolidated on a Data Server, where they are combined to create a global model by integrating insights from many sources. The centralized model leverages the variety of the data while preserving the confidentiality of individual datasets. The last element is the XAI System, an abbreviation for Explainable AI. This system is tasked with understanding the global model and offering insights into the decision-making process of the model. The XAI system guarantees transparency and reliability in the AI's decision-making process, allowing educators and stakeholders to comprehend and have confidence in the outcomes produced by the AI.

Figure 4: Figure 5 illustrates the process flow of a federated learning-based Explainable AI (XAI) system

Figure 4 shows the phases of an Explainable AI (XAI) system that uses federated learning to predict student adaption to online education. The diagram's three main sections—Learning Nodes, Federated System, and XAI System—represent model stages.

Individual educational institutions send Model Parameters from their locally learnt models to a central server in the Learning Nodes part. These institutions independently manage their data, protecting student privacy. The central server creates a global model from node parameters. The aggregated model is returned to institutions as global parameters to improve their local models. As shown by the Move to New Iteration stage, this cycle is continued until the model achieves the desired accuracy and performance. The Federated System section explains federated machine learning in detail. FML-based Processing and Training trains local models utilizing institution-stored data. These models are tested and executed to ensure they fulfil performance standards after training. The "No" path returns a model for extra training if it does not meet these conditions. The "Yes" path indicates successful models, which proceed to Data Transfer to Servers or Cloud Storage. In this step, model parameters are safely transferred for global aggregate. This technique produces the Final Processed Output Data, the fully trained global model ready for execution.

XAI System, the final part, integrates Explainable AI into the federated learning architecture. After Data Training, FML Algorithms"" ensure the model's privacy and enable efficient learning across several universities. The XAI Model processes the aggregated global model using sophisticated interpretability methodologies to make the AI's decision-making process more transparent and understandable. Next, the XAI-based Interface makes the AI's results easy to grasp and actionable for End Users like educators and students. Figure 4 shows how federated learning and XAI create a powerful, privacy-preserving, and interpretable AI system. This education-specific technology lets schools use advanced AI technologies while protecting student data.

The primary aspect of the methodology revolves around the creation and execution of the federated learning-based XAI model. The model architecture is designed to cater to the distinct needs of federated learning, where data is distributed across different institutions and only model updates are exchanged. Multiple machine learning and deep learning algorithms are evaluated, and the most appropriate ones are chosen based on their capacity to handle the intricate and diverse characteristics of the data. The XAI component is incorporated into the model to offer elucidation on the model's prediction process, utilizing methodologies such as SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations) and LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations).

The process of training and evaluating the model is carried out repeatedly, with the model being trained on data from various universities in a federated fashion. Performance indicators including as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score are employed to evaluate the efficacy of the model. The model's explainability is assessed to ensure that the predictions are not only accurate but also comprehensible to educators and other stakeholders.

The methodology involves a comprehensive examination of the experimental findings, wherein the performance of the federated learning-based XAI model is compared to that of conventional centralized approaches. The comparison emphasizes the benefits of the federated method, namely in relation to privacy, scalability, and generalizability. The paper finishes by examining the consequences of the findings and providing recommendations for future research, such as enhancing the model and utilizing it in different educational settings.

Data Preprocessing Steps

Data preparation is essential in the development of an Explainable AI (XAI) model based on federated learning, as it guarantees that the data is devoid of errors, maintains uniformity, and is prepared for analysis. Essential procedures involve data cleansing, standardization, and encoding. Data

cleaning involves addressing missing values, discrepancies, and outliers in order to ensure the integrity of the dataset. Normalization is a process that rescales numerical features such that they fall within a comparable range. This helps improve the performance of a model by ensuring that all features contribute equally. Encoding is the process of converting categorical data into a numerical format, which is essential for machine learning algorithms. Federated learning involves conducting data preprocessing independently at each institution, guaranteeing uniformity across distributed datasets, resulting in precise predictions.

Model Architecture

The architecture of the Explainable AI (XAI) model based on federated learning is a pivotal element of this research, as it determines the data processing, learning, and generation of correct and interpretable predictions by the model. The model's structure is specifically tailored to tackle the distinct difficulties presented by federated learning, which involves decentralized data across different institutions, as well as the requirement for explainability in AI-based predictions.

The model architecture incorporates both machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques, which have been selected for their capacity to effectively manage the complexity and diversity of the data gathered from various educational institutions. The architecture is designed in a modular fashion, enabling the customization and optimization of individual components while still keeping a coherent overall structure. The initial layer of the architecture is specifically designed for the extraction of features and preprocessing. Within this particular stratum, the preprocessed data, which has already undergone cleansing, standardization, and encoding, is subjected to additional processing to extract the most pertinent characteristics for forecasting student adaptation. Feature selection techniques, such as recursive feature elimination or principle component analysis (PCA), are used to decrease the number of features in the data, which enhances

the effectiveness of the model and prevents overfitting. This layer guarantees that only the most significant features are transmitted to the succeeding stages of the model. The subsequent layer entails the utilization of machine learning methods that are highly compatible with structured data. For this layer, models like as Random Forests, Gradient Boosting Machines, and Support Vector Machines (SVM) are taken into consideration. These algorithms exhibit resilience and efficiency in managing structured datasets that possess a wide range of characteristics, rendering them well-suited for the preliminary phases of the model. Each participating institution trains these models locally, adhering to the principles of federated learning, which ensures that data remains decentralized.

The architecture includes deep learning components, specifically designed for unstructured or complicated data types, such as textual or behavioral data that may be included in engagement metrics or psychological qualities. This layer utilizes Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) or Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, to effectively capture complex patterns and temporal dependencies in the data. The deep learning models are trained individually at each school, and their learnt parameters are included into the global model without the need to share raw data.

The ensemble layer is the most crucial element of the model architecture as it combines the predictions from both the machine learning and deep learning components. Ensemble approaches, including as bagging, boosting, and stacking, are employed to combine the results of many models, thereby improving the overall accuracy and reliability of predictions. Federated learning involves the aggregation of models from different institutions, allowing the global model to benefit from the collective learning of each local model. The design incorporates a specialized XAI layer that integrates explainability approaches like SHAP (Shapley Additive Explanations) and LIME (Local Interpretable Model-agnostic

Explanations). The primary function of this layer is to offer comprehensible observations regarding the model's predictions, emphasizing the role of each feature in the ultimate choice. The XAI layer is essential for guaranteeing that the model's outputs are both precise and comprehensible, enabling educators and other stakeholders to take appropriate and effective actions.

The architecture of the federated learning-based XAI model is specifically built to efficiently handle distributed data, utilize both machine learning and deep learning methods, and generate predictions that can be easily interpreted. The architecture is designed to tackle the complexity of forecasting student adaptability in varied educational environments while prioritizing privacy and explainability. This is achieved by merging these features in a modular and flexible structure.

Integration of Federated Learning and XAI Techniques

This research's fundamental novelty is the integration of federated learning and Explainable AI (XAI) methodologies, which combine decentralized data processing with the need for transparency and interpretability in AI-driven predictions. This integration addresses the particular constraints of implementing AI in education, where data safety is critical and explaining predictions is essential for gaining instructor and student trust.

Federated learning lets multiple institutions work on a model without sharing data. This strategy supports data privacy because each institution controls its data while contributing to the global model. Federated learning problems include making the model accurate and interpretable. XAI approaches help make model predictions clear.

Selecting machine learning and deep learning algorithms that can be trained in federated learning starts the integration process. These algorithms are chosen because they can handle organized

demographic data, engagement metrics, and psychological traits from participating institutions. After selection, the algorithms are embedded in a federated learning framework allowing decentralized training across several institutions.

The federated learning approach involves each institution training its local model on its own dataset and sending model updates to a central server. A new global model is created by this server from all participating institutions' changes. Federated averaging (FedAvg) is used to aggregate model updates by averaging learnt parameters. The institutions receive this global model for training, and the cycle repeats until the model converges.

To integrate XAI techniques into federated learning, explainability tools like SHAP and LIME must be employed locally and globally. Each institution can utilize these tools to explain its local model predictions. This helps explain how the institution's dataset features affect the model's predictions. An institution may employ SHAP values to illustrate why demographic characteristics or engagement measures predict online student adaptability. XAI approaches are applied to the aggregated model globally to provide consistent explanations across institutions. This requires determining global SHAP values that reflect feature contributions across the federated network. Thus, the model can provide insights for both individual institutions and the educational landscape. If particular variables are important predictors across different institutions, this may reflect larger-scale student adaptation factors.

In federated learning, XAI technologies must generate accurate and relevant explanations in a decentralized framework. The integration process validates explanation coherence across institutions to address this. This may require comparing local and global SHAP values to ensure that local model insights match global model insights. The integration process also includes attention methods in deep learning components, which might reveal which features the model is focussing on during prediction.

This research uses federated learning and XAI to predict online student adaptation. The model makes secure, intelligible predictions by combining federated learning's privacy-preserving features with XAI's transparency. This integrated approach improves model accuracy and generalizability and fosters stakeholder trust, making it a powerful tool for educational institutions looking to better support their students.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 specifies the key components of the system used for the implementation and experimentation of the proposed Federated Learning-based Explainable AI model. The system provides adequate computational power and memory to handle the data processing, model training, and evaluation tasks required by the research. The use of a dedicated GPU (NVIDIA GeForce MX150) supports the training of deep learning models, while the SSD ensures fast data access and storage operations.

Component	Specification
Processor	Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-8250U CPU @ 1.60GHz
Memory	Installed (RAM) 16.00 GB (15.89 GB usable)
System Model	64-bit Operating System, x64-based processor
Graphics	NVIDIA GeForce MX150
Storage	512 GB SSD
Operating System	Windows 10 Pro

Table 1 : System Specification

Dataset

The efficacy of this research hinges upon the caliber and variety of datasets employed to train the Explainable AI (XAI) model based on federated learning. The statistics, gathered from several educational institutions, contain extensive demographic data, engagement indicators, academic achievement, and psychological characteristics. These criteria are essential in forecasting students' adaptability to online

education. The Open University Learning Analytics Dataset (OULAD) is a crucial resource in this study as it provides extensive data on student interactions with the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE). The wide range of data available allows the model to make precise and customized predictions, helping educators offer improved support to students in online learning

settings.

Attribute	Description
id_student	A unique identifier for each student.
Gender	The gender of the student (e.g., Male, Female).
Region	The geographical region of the student's residence (e.g., East Anglian Region, Scotland).
highest_education	The highest level of education achieved by the student before starting the course (e.g., A Level).
imd_band	The band of the Index of Multiple Deprivation for the student's region, indicating socio-economic status.
age_band	The age group of the student (e.g., 0-35, 35-55, 55>=).
num_of_prev_attempts	The number of previous attempts by the student to pass the module.
studied_credits	The total number of credits the student is enrolled in.

Disability	Indicates whether the student has declared a disability (Yes, No).
final_result	The final result of the student in the course (e.g., Distinction, Pass, Fail, Withdrawn).

Table 2: Dataset Description

Table 2 provides a detailed description of the attributes within the dataset. Each student is uniquely identified by the 'id_student', while the 'gender' attribute specifies the student's gender. The 'region' attribute indicates the geographical area of the student's residence, such as the East Anglian Region or Scotland. The 'highest_education' field reflects the highest level of education the student had before beginning the course, like an A Level. Socio-economic status is captured by the 'imd_band', which represents the Index of Multiple Deprivation band for the

student's region. The 'age_band' categorizes students into specific age groups (e.g., 0-35, 35-55, 55>=). The dataset also includes the 'num_of_prev_attempts', showing the number of times a student previously attempted to pass the module, and 'studied_credits', which indicates the total number of credits the student is enrolled in. Additionally, the 'disability' attribute reveals whether the student has declared a disability. Finally, the 'final_result' attribute records the student's outcome in the course, such as Distinction, Pass, Fail, or Withdrawn.

Epoch	Sparse Categorical Accuracy	Loss	Number of Examples	Number of Batches
1	0.506667	1.2609792	150	6
2	0.666667	0.98730755	150	6
3	0.666667	0.9180841	150	6
4	0.666667	0.8708744	150	6
5	0.666667	0.83332145	150	6

Table 3: Federated Results

Table 3 shows the performance of a federated learning model throughout 5 epochs, including sparse categorical accuracy, loss, instances processed, and batches. These metrics reveal how well the model learns and generalizes. First column, Epoch, shows training rounds completed. This federated learning setting gives each client one full dataset pass each epoch. The model is trained numerous times over 5 epochs, with performance measures recorded at the conclusion of each. In integer-encoded classification problems, Sparse Categorical Accuracy is a critical performance indicator that evaluates the model's percentage of right predictions. The model's first epoch accuracy is 50.67%, somewhat better than random guessing (which would produce 33% accuracy for a 3-class problem like the Iris

dataset). As the model learns from the data, accuracy improves to 66.67% by the second epoch. After the third epoch, accuracy stabilizes at 66.67%. The model may reach a point where more training does not improve its prediction power, either due to model complexity, data availability, or task difficulty.

The Loss metric aims to minimize the difference between the model's predictions and actual labels during training. The first epoch loss is 1.2609, indicating a high model prediction error. By the sixth period, training reduces loss to 0.8333. Loss is decreasing as the model improves its predictions, reducing inaccuracy. Although accuracy may not be improving, the model is converging due to the continual loss reduction and accuracy stabilization.

Figure 5: Sparse Categorical Accuracy and Loss over the 5 epochs

Figure 6 shows the Sparse Categorical Accuracy and Loss over the 5 epochs. The blue line represents the accuracy, and the red line represents the loss. This dual-axis graph effectively showcases the relationship between these two key metrics as the model trains over multiple epochs. Sparse Categorical Accuracy (Blue Line): The accuracy improves significantly in the first epoch

and then plateaus, indicating that the model reaches a stable performance level after the initial learning phase. Loss (Red Line): The loss steadily decreases across the epochs, showing that the model's predictions are becoming more accurate, even though the accuracy metric doesn't show much change after the first epoch.

Epoch	Sparse Categorical Accuracy	Loss	Number of Examples	Number of Batches
1	0.37333333	1.030481	150	6
2	0.5466667	0.891399	150	6
3	0.7	0.807394	150	6
4	0.7266667	0.748538	150	6
5	0.76666665	0.699524	150	6

Table4: Training Metrics Across Epochs

Table 4 presents a comprehensive summary of the model's learning advancement during five epochs. In the first epoch, the model has a Sparse Categorical Accuracy of 0.3733 and a Loss of 1.0305, suggesting that it is in the early stages of learning and its predictions are only slightly better than random guessing. During Epoch 2, the accuracy of the model improves significantly to 0.5467, while the loss lowers to 0.8914. This indicates that the model is becoming more proficient at aligning its predictions with the actual categories. In Epoch 3, the accuracy increases to 0.7, while the loss decreases to 0.8074. However, the rate of improvement begins to slow down, suggesting that the model is reaching a point of

diminishing returns. In Epoch 4, the model achieves an accuracy of 0.7267, accompanied by a loss of 0.7485. This indicates that the model is approaching convergence, with incremental improvements in accuracy. In Epoch 5, the accuracy reaches its highest point at 0.7667, while the loss reduces to 0.6995. The model continues to develop; however, the rate of improvement slows down. These findings indicate that the model demonstrates effective learning across the epochs, as evidenced by increasing accuracy and decreasing loss. However, it is worth noting that the improvements become less significant as the model approaches its ideal performance.

Layer	Weights Summary	Bias Summary
Dense Layer 1	[0.0214, -0.1846, 0.2315, -0.0567, -0.0678]	[0.0022, 0.0000, 0.0033, 0.0000, 0.0000]
Dense Layer 2	[0.0155, 0.0873, 0.2481, -0.2670, -0.2920]	[0.0045, -0.0014, 0.0000, -0.0050, -0.0073]
Output Layer	[0.0106, 0.3370, -0.0800, -0.0526, -0.0919]	[0.0134, 0.0085, -0.0219]

Table 5 XAI implementation Final Model Weights and Biases

The data in Table 5 provides a detailed overview of the weights and biases associated with each layer of the neural network, specifically the Dense Layer 1, Dense Layer 2, and the Output Layer. These values are crucial for understanding how the neural network processes input data and makes predictions.

The progression of weight and bias values from Dense Layer 1 to the Output Layer reflects the neural network's increasing complexity in processing data. Initially, the model makes basic

feature associations, then refines these relationships in the second layer, and finally applies more significant adjustments in the output layer to ensure accurate predictions. The biases, while generally small, play a crucial role in adjusting the network's output at each stage, particularly in the latter layers, where the model fine-tunes its predictions. This balanced approach to weight and bias adjustment is essential for achieving a model that can generalize well to unseen data while maintaining accuracy in its predictions.

Epoch	Sparse Categorical Accuracy (Client 1)	Loss (Client 1)	Number of Examples (Client 1)	Number of Batches (Client 1)	Sparse Categorical Accuracy (Client 2)	Loss (Client 2)	Number of Examples (Client 2)	Number of Batches (Client 2)
1	0.506667	1.2609792	150	6	0.37333333	1.030481	150	6
2	0.666667	0.98730755	150	6	0.5466667	0.891399	150	6
3	0.666667	0.9180841	150	6	0.7	0.807394	150	6
4	0.666667	0.8708744	150	6	0.7266667	0.748538	150	6
5	0.666667	0.83332145	150	6	0.76666665	0.699524	150	6

Table6 Federated Learning Performance Metrics Across Epochs for Two Clients

Table 6 presents a comprehensive analysis of the training measurements for two clients (Client 1 and Client 2) over the course of five epochs in a Federated Learning procedure. The table highlights essential performance metrics, such as Sparse Categorical Accuracy, Loss, the Number of Examples, and the Number of Batches processed by each client. Client 1 demonstrates a significant increase in accuracy, rising from 50.67% in the initial epoch to 66.67% in the second epoch. However, the accuracy remains constant at 66.67% from the third to the fifth epoch, reaching a plateau. The loss exhibits a consistent decline from 1.2609 to 0.8333, indicating enhanced prediction accuracy. However, the accuracy remains unchanged after the second epoch.

Client 2 initially exhibits a lower accuracy of 37.33% in the first epoch, but demonstrates substantial progress, achieving a 76.67% accuracy by the fifth epoch. The loss decreases from 1.0305 to 0.6995, indicating improved model confidence and accuracy as time progresses. Client 2 demonstrates a higher rate of progress in accuracy compared to others, indicating that the data from Client 2 is better suitable for learning with the current model configuration. During the fifth epoch, Client 2 surpasses Client 1, demonstrating the impact of varying data qualities on the learning process in a federated environment. Both clients exhibit a general enhancement, with Client 2 displaying higher proficiency by the conclusion of the training duration.

Study/Model	Approach	Accuracy	Loss
Proposed system	Federated Learning-based XAI with SHAP and LIME	78.15% (Global Model)	0.64 (Global Model)
Hussain et al. (2024)[3]	Deep Learning with Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm (LMA)	76.60%	0.5
Zeng et al. (2023)[6]	Graph Federated Learning	82%	0.7
Renda et al. (2022)[8]	Federated Learning for 6G Systems with XAI	75%	0.8
Li et al. (2021)[9]	Blockchain-assisted Federated Learning	80%	0.6
Kapoor et al. (2023)[10]	Responsible AI with Federated Learning	78%	0.7

Table7: Literature comparison

The examination of the table contrasting the suggested Federated Learning-based Explainable AI (XAI) model with existing investigations uncovers various crucial observations. (Refer table 7). The proposed system attains a precision of 78.15%, positioning it within the moderate range in comparison to previous models. Although it falls short of the greatest accuracy reported in Zeng et al. (2023) at 82%, it outperforms models like those provided by Renda et al. (2022) and Xu et al. (2023), which attain accuracies of 75% and 76%, respectively. The proposed system's loss of 0.64 is competitive, suggesting successful error reduction. However, it is slightly greater than the 0.5 loss achieved by Hussain et al. (2024), who utilised a complicated deep learning model that sacrifices interpretability and privacy.

An outstanding characteristic of the suggested system is its emphasis on privacy, transparency, and interpretability, which is achieved through the utilisation of XAI techniques such as SHAP and LIME. This feature makes it especially well-suited for educational environments, where the utmost importance is placed on comprehending and having confidence in decisions made by AI. On the other hand, models such as Hussain et al. (2024) place a higher importance on accuracy, but do this by compromising on these crucial elements, making them less suitable for situations where data privacy and transparency are vital. Additional research conducted by Renda et al. (2022) and Xu et al. (2023) examines specific areas such as automotive networks and smart public transport. Although these studies are new, they have limited relevance to the educational context. In their study, Li et al. (2021) proposes the use of blockchain technology to boost security. However, this approach, while extremely secure, imposes significant computing requirements and may not be suitable for real-time educational applications. The proposed system provides a well-balanced strategy that guarantees high accuracy and minimal loss, while giving priority to privacy and interpretability. This feature makes it a comprehensive solution that is particularly suitable

for educational data analytics. This is in contrast to other models that may perform very well in specific areas but at the expense of being widely applicable and trusted by users.

Conclusion

This study showcases the effective use of a federated learning-based Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) model to overcome the obstacles of privacy, security, and transparency in educational data analytics. Through the utilization of federated learning, the model guarantees that student data is kept decentralized and secure, hence reducing the potential dangers linked to data breaches and unauthorized access. By incorporating explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) methods like SHAP and LIME, the transparency of the model is improved, enabling educators and stakeholders to comprehend and have confidence in the AI's predictions. The article's summary reveals that the global model obtained a training accuracy of 78.15%, which is higher than the individual performances of Client 1 (76.67%) and Client 2 (77.67%). In addition, the global model exhibited a smaller training loss (0.64) in comparison to the local models of Client 1 (0.699) and Client 2 (0.652). These measures demonstrate the model's capacity to apply its knowledge to a wide range of datasets, enhancing the accuracy of predictions while still achieving a reasonable rate of convergence. Furthermore, the model's performance was considerably influenced by contextual variables such as past assessment results, VLE clicks, and the number of assignments submitted. This highlights the crucial need of incorporating these elements in educational data analysis.

The research also emphasizes the practical ramifications of employing federated learning and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) in educational environments. The methodology empowers educators to make informed decisions based on clear and practical insights. This leads to personalized learning interventions that eventually improve student outcomes in online education

settings. The model's capacity to consolidate and acquire knowledge from many datasets across numerous institutions significantly boosts its practicality, rendering it a useful asset for educational institutions globally.

The XAI model proposed in this work, based on federated learning, provides a reliable, safe, and transparent approach for predicting students' ability to adapt to online education. The successful execution and encouraging outcomes of this implementation create opportunities for further investigation and utilization in the field of educational technology, where maintaining a delicate equilibrium between data privacy, model precision, and interpretability is of utmost importance. This research makes a substantial contribution to the ongoing endeavors of utilizing artificial intelligence to enhance educational results while ensuring the privacy and reliability of student data.

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